

Innovative Women in Digital Technology Contributed to a Society

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Abstract

Women played an important role in the development of computer science. The role of Information of Communication Technology as a tool for development has attracted all the areas. Non Government Organization has been established in private sector. Strategic partnership has been developed with donors, the private sector and civil society and working group and the task forces have been established to enhance interagency collaboration throughout the world. The technologies comprise of a complex and heterogeneous set of goods, applications and services to produce, process, distribute the transform information. This article describes the brief history of computer science. And it deals with the influence of designing and programming the first electronic computer languages, while laying the ground work for women expanding involvement in science.

Keywords: Computer science, empowerment, pioneer, programming languages and women.

Introduction

Women in computing have shaped the evolution of information technology. They were among the first programmers in the early-20th century, and contributed substantially to the industry. As technology and practices altered, the role of women as programmers has also changed, and the recorded history of the field has downplayed achievements of women. Since the 18th century, women have developed scientific computations, including Nicole-ReineLepaute's prediction of Halley's Comet, and Maria Mitchell's computation of the motion of Venus. The first algorithm intended to be executed by a computer was designed by Ada Lovelace who was a pioneer in the field. Grace Hopper was the first person to design a compiler for a programming language. Throughout the 19th and early-20th century, and up to the World War II, programming was predominantly done by women; significant examples include the Harvard Computers, codebreaking at Bletchley Park. After the 1960s, the "soft work" that had been dominated by women evolved into modern software, and the importance of women started decreasing. Many women continued to make significant and important contributions to the IT industry, and attempts were made

to readdress the gender disparity in the industry. In the 21st century, women held leadership roles in multiple tech companies, such as Meg Whitman, president and the chief executive officer of Hewlett Packard Enterprise, and Marissa Mayer, president and CEO of Yahoo! from July 2012 to June 2017 and previously a long-time executive, usability leader, and and the key spokes person at Google. This paper is organised as follows. The session two brief the history, the session three describes the five influential women in the filed of computer science and the last session detailed about conclusion.

Brief History

A history lesson on computer science, not often taught in Computer Science classes: women were the first software engineers, until men actively pushed them out. Beginning in the late 1960's, men realized that programming was actually really hard, and prestigious. It was lucrative and valuable, and (some) men didn't want women enjoying all the benefits of that. As the researcher and historian Nathan Ensmenger helped to reveal, professional organizations, smear marketing and ad campaigns were created that discouraged the hiring of women into computer science and programming roles. Meanwhile, aptitude tests were made (by men) that favored men in their evaluation steps, and the answers to those tests were circulated across male-only groups like fraternities. In the early- to mid-1980's, another major factor compounded upon this: video game consoles came to market, and as they were marketed as toys, their makers were asked to decide which (gendered) section of the stores they would be sold in. Instead of arguing that everyone should love video games, the makers simply chose boys-and the marketing followed suit. Fast-forward 20 to 30 years, and the children from this era have become grown ups carrying those very same false messages they were told as kids: "technology is for boys, not girls." Damore is one such example. His memo shows that he still thinks this way, despite his field of work being invented largely by women, who dominated it first. Nick Coghlan helpfully reminded that these gender ratios are country-dependent. For the year 2011, women in the U.S. made up only 18% of undergrads in Computer Science and Engineering, whilst in India that number was 42%. In 2005 in India, looking at CS alone, women earned 55% of the Bachelor's of Science degrees. The cultural difference is key: in the U.S., CS is culturally tainted as a "male" field, but in India both men and women see the field as something for all genders, and people aspire to work in it accordingly. But let's look at a closer comparison, our neighbors to the North: in Canada, women comprised ~27% of CS enrollments during the period 2006 to 2010. In the US, that number was below 20%.

Five Influential Women in Computer Science

Ada Byron Lady Lovelace, was born in 1815, and her single mother raised her to love science and math. In 1843, Byron wrote an article forecasting a device that could create images and aid scientists. She conceptualized the computer program, which she imagined as a set of instructions that a machine could follow to make calculations. Ada Byron was gravely ill throughout much of her life, and she died at the age of 36. But her works helped civilization to imagine an exciting new world. Ada Byron, Countess of Lovelace, was a mathematician Milbanke, who collaborated with Charles Babbage on the difference and Analytical Engines, which are regarded as the theoretical foundation for the modern computer. Lovelace was 17 years old when she first met Babbage. When he showed her the Difference Engine, she immediately dubbed it a "thinking machine," recognizing its value as a tool for science and mathematics.

Grace Murray Hopper was admired and respected not only for her technological achievements but also for her energy. Enthusiasm, willingness to serve as a mentor. Her career was fascinating and varied. She earned a PhD in mathematics from Yale and taught at Vassar. She worked at the

Harvard University Computation Laboratory, and she became a rear admiral in the Navy. Admiral Hopper died in 1992, yet her impact endures. She argued that programmers should share their work so that computers could evolve faster. She helped to assemble computer compilers, systems that can translate programming languages and codes. She also labored to make programming more understandable to non-experts. As a result, more businesses were able to utilize computer technology. She was responsible for developing the FLOW-MATIC programming language at the time. The COBOL community, an industry-wide group partially supervised by Hopper, used Flow-Matic as the model.

In the early 1950s, the Weizmann Institute of Science in Isreal accelerated that country's participation in the information revolution by building a computer called the WEIZAC, closely modeled on von Neumann's Institute for Advanced Study (IAS) computer. It was built to solve problems in applied mathematics and classical physics for the Applied Mathematics Department. The ImaEstrin, a Cornell University professor and the daughter of distinguished computer scientists, is remarkably gifted and prolific. While teaching at UCLA, Estrin devised mobile tools that gather and evaluate data about their surrounding environments. She was one of the initial two engineers to work under Gerald Estrin's in the design and development of the machine. Estrin's previous experience in working with von Neumann on the IAS project facilitated her design efforts. Additionally, she's known for building application program interfaces that let users manage their personal data. At the top of that, Estrin cofounded Open Health, a nonprofit that allows people to collect the medical information they need at free of cost.

Marissa Mayer, currently the CEO of Yahoo, studied computers and artificial intelligence at Stanford University. After receiving her master's degree from that college, she became one of the first people that Google hired. She spent 13 years in that company, serving as an engineer, a spokesperson, and more. In 2012, she began leading Yahoo.

Jean E Summet. joined IBM in 1961. While at IBM, she was responsible for the development of FORMAC, the first widely used language for performing symbolic mathematics. In 1969, she published, programming Languages: History and fundamentals, which many consider to be the standard work on programming languages. She worked with Mary Kenneth Keller. She is from Cleveland Ohio Sisters of the Charity was the one of the first women to receive Philosophy Doctorate in computer science in the United States. Keller felt that women should be involved in computer science and especially in the field of information specialist. She says that "An information explosion, among others, and it's certainly obvious that information is of no use unless it's available." Keller's vision extended beyond education and reached towards artificial intelligence." For the first time people can mechanically simulate the cognitive process.

Conclusion

This article documents the involvement of pioneering women in the beginning days of computer science, from their work on the first machines to their development of the early programming languages. The influence of women who were involved in original work that gave ground for breaking technical development to generate new ideas in the realm of computer science.

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